

DELIVERABLE

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Authors:

Luca M.C. Giberti (QED)
Raffaella Santucci (QED)

Reviewers:

Vincenzo Grillo (CNR)
Enzo Rotunno (CNR)

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This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The purpose of this deliverable is to provide a summary of the work on the MINEON Mascot and ensuing 1. project Logo and 2. Website, as well its sections, its technical infrastructures, and its related services.

This deliverable complies with the MINEON DoA outlined in Work Package 3 - Innovation management & Exploitation [Months: 1-8].

It particularly satisfies specifications outlined in Task 3.1: Dissemination & Exploitation (M1-M8), thus providing a reference point for all necessary actions regarding the promotion of MINEON's Web presence.

The promotional elements addressed in the document are the design and definition of the MINEON Mascot, Logo, and the related graphic elements & rules, which determine the Website graphics and layout.

The current document is comprised of 6 Chapters, an Executive Summary, Conclusions and an Annex.

The first Chapter describes the MINEON branding and visual identity strategies, which notably includes specific paragraphs devoted to the description of the MINEON Mascot and MINEON Logo.

Chapters 2, 3, 4 present respectively an overview of MINEON's Website layout and structure, its technical infrastructure and the tools it offers, its integration and interactions with Social Networks and additional services (e.g., web feeds, analysis tools, etc.).

Chapter 5 describes the workflow of the editorial team and the content of the website's various sections.

1 THE MINEON VISUAL IDENTITY: MASCOT AND LOGO

1.1 MINEON VISUAL IDENTITY

1.1.1 Overall philosophy

The study of a visual identity for MINEON began right at the beginning of the project. Due to the specialist nature of the subject matter, it is challenging to devise a set of graphic objects and rules that are both meaningful and striking, and which work for different target audiences.

Since careful dissemination of the project's results is of great value not only to academia & the industry, but also to lay circles, a vigorous push towards engagement has been a guiding principle in our work since the beginning. We feel that a low standard of design and copywriting has in the past been the cause of (otherwise-excellent) science projects' limited success in attracting a wider audience. Luckily, thanks also to the efforts of the European Commission, the situation has evolved quickly in recent years: there is a growing investment in communication, branding, and public relations aimed towards a wider audience.

In keeping pace with these positive developments, we sought to build MINEON's visual strategy based on the strengths of its very successful parent project, Q-SORT.

In particular, in order to make the best use of the existing Q-SORT audiences, which took more than three years of efforts to accrete, we sought to evoke a sense of continuity with it. This was done by adopting the same visually rigorous approach for the graphics, including the same compositional and typographical rules. Such an approach is driven principally by an emphasis on the following elements: 1) the beauty and richness of meaning of the concepts that the project entails; 2) the scientific excellence of its endeavour and of the participating institutions; 3) the beauty of the imagery generated by the research work pertaining to the project.

At the same time, our intention was also to instil a sense of evolution with respect to Q-SORT, to signify the shift from pure, proof-of-principle research to the development and validation of advanced prototypes of higher and higher TRL. This was achieved by using a different palette (black, white, gray, and yellow instead of black, white, gray, and red) and, most of all, by combining Q-SORT's rigorous, awe-inducing visual language with the immediate potency of cartoons - which in our case signal the shift from an almost purely academic pursuit to a more practical one. Therefore we sought to develop a cartoon mascot whose looks and palette would marry well with the existing system of typographic rules. The fact that it is a character doesn't just make communication much more immediate (due to its rich facial repertoire of facial expressions and poses), but also embodies a spirit of volition, a renewed drive. Crucially, the cartoon element makes the MINEON graphics stand out as unique in the panorama of scientific and corporate-scientific communication.

The successful marriage of these two different languages -the rigorous graphics & rules of Q-SORT with the ease and immediacy of the cartoon- creates an interesting and pleasing contrast. Also, crucially, this arrangement allows further future tuning of the overall 'tone' of the communication, by increasing or decreasing the size, the relevance of the position, and the expressiveness of the various cartoon instances - see the Website section (chapter 2) for more details. Of course, if required by the corporate profile of the eventual spin-off company, the cartoon component can also be entirely switched off. This 'emotional tuneability' is desirable given the different target audiences of MINEON and of other future post-Q-SORT developments.

1.1.2 Branding

In accordance with the parameters of our DoA, a professionally-conducted study of MINEON's branding was thus undertaken. At the core of our efforts, as always, is the intention of developing an overall 'look-and-feel', a unique and easily identifiable personality to be consistently declined across all platforms used during dissemination. This undertaking includes the following branding elements:

1. Basic Elements

i. *Brand mascot*: the central character that is synonymous with MINEON, the incarnation of its spirit of enthusiasm, pragmatism, and creativity. The Mascot is depicted in various instances, depending on the needs (see Chapter 2 on the project Website). It is also the project's face in thumbnails and favicons for social media, browsers, and mobile shortcuts.

ii. *Brand logo*, i.e. the symbol through which the project is easily recognised, in both print and electronic media, as well as headed paper. This is determined by one instance of the Mascot, together with the MINEON title (see Chapter 1.2).

ii. *Branding architecture*, that is a coherent system of typographical rules, visual relations, and hierarchies between the Mascot, the Logo and the (typo)graphical elements connectable to them (e.g. the MINEON Mascot and event titles). In particular, the new [black, white, gray, yellow] colour palette was conceived as a part of a coherent integrated system of colour coding, wherein the red, yellow, and green components correspond to different stages in innovation development, corresponding thus to the new EIC structuring:

<u>Lead colour</u>	<u>Corresponding EC project</u>	<u>Corresponding EC funding scheme</u>
red	Q-SORT	FET Open / EIC Pathfinder Open
yellow	MINEON	FET Innovation Launchpad / EIC Transition
green	name t.b.c.	EIC Accelerator

2. Web

i. Templates for the web pages that are compatible with WordPress and the CMS of the website. In particular, these include: a. main website page; b. news & events subpages template for the News subsection; c. contacts subsection, etc.

A vast selection of graphs, illustrations, as well as TEM images and motifs was assembled for the visual identity study. Graphic artists were also briefed qualitatively on various aspects of the science behind the project and of the challenges involved in the project activities. The first element arising from the visual identity study was the design of the MINEON Mascot.

1.2 THE MINEON MASCOT

As the first graphic element to be designed for the project, the Mascot can be thought of as the cornerstone upon which everything else will be built in terms of graphics and overall outreach & dissemination.

The Mascot has to concurrently fulfil several functions, since it should be: instantly recognisable, elegant, representative of the project, simple, easy to reproduce at various different sizes and on many different media. The cartoon Mascot fulfils all these functions almost effortlessly and, compared to an abstract graphic logo, also has immediate evocative power.

1.2.1 Mascot design

The work on the Mascot started with brainstorming between QED's creative director, Luca Giberti, and the cartoonist, Enrico Macchiavello. The overall arc of the project was explained, as well as its relationship with Q-SORT. The relevant underlying physical concepts and technological implications were explained. From the outset we sought to provide a graphical representation of some of these concepts and/or of the experimental procedures that are characteristic of the project. We explored and evolved several ideas that could embody the overall spirit of enthusiastic quest underlying the project - communicating a sense of joy and of movement.

Naturally, we had to take into account the use of the Mascot within the intended Website design. Therefore, the only self-imposed limits at this stage were two: 1. the knowledge that the system of graphic rules for the Website and other graphic assets would have been rigorous and largely based on Q-SORT's; 2. the fact that the new Website palette would have featured yellow instead of red, which had been decided beforehand. The Mascot would thus have to fit well within these constraints. Another consideration we kept in mind throughout the design phase was the suitability of the Mascot to be animated as part of a possible future ident to be spliced at the start of video assets, in future, post-MINEON developments.

The starting point was a series of exploratory sketches and renderings:

Figure 1. The first early proposal for the Mascot, called Rough 01

Figure 2. the $L=1$ spiral wavefront that is referenced in Rough 01

In Rough 01, the leitmotiv of the spiral monocle was obviously chosen so as to represent the spiral wavefront determined by the electron spiral phase plate (eSPP) on the electron wavefunction. The monocle symbolises the fact that the eSPP can be thought of as a form of ‘prescription glasses’ for the TEM, improving its ‘vision’ through edge enhancement. The Q in the belt buckle signals the connection with Q-SORT.

Rough 02 kept the Q-SORT buckle but transferred the spiral theme onto the hair of the character and made the reference to the flower-shaped voltage divider developed at CNR explicit:

Figure 3. The second early proposal for the Mascot, called Rough 02

Figure 4. The voltage divider design that is referenced in Rough 02

Rough 03 stressed on the spectacles concept, and featured electron phase patterns in the trousers as well; the Q-SORT reference was shifted onto a new custom hat:

Figure 5. The third early proposal for the Mascot, called Rough 03

The three proposals were weighted one against the other according to the various expected 'scenarios of use' in the Website (see Chapter 2). Selected collaborators were also polled and provided feedback. Special attention was paid to any possible accidental negative association -e.g. with stereotypes or with existing negative characters- that the proposed characters might trigger.

Further specific graphic feedback from Luca Giberti sought to make Rough 01 even more friendly and brought about its advanced version:

Figure 6. The advanced version of Rough 01

The latter was deemed to be superior to all the other designs and thus chosen as the Mascot. Various instances of the Mascot were then developed for the needs of the Logo, Website, and favicons (see following chapters).

The Mascot was well received and garnered the praise of the partners.

1.2.2 Development of Mascot instances for the Website and for Whatsapp Stickers

In order to provide the required counterpunctual contrast, at first the Website was structured and developed independently of the Mascot (see Chapter 2). In other words, the initial requirement was to design a Website that was in line with Q-SORT's and that worked 'dry', i.e. without cartoons.

As stated in **1.2.1 Mascot design**, the only a priori choices at the start of both Mascot and Website designs were 1. adopting existing Q-SORT rules for the Website and 2. featuring yellow instead of red in the otherwise monochrome palette.

Throughout the Website design phase, we followed QED's customary guiding principles of clarity and simplicity, which notably entail the adoption of a minimalistic tonal and chromatic palette, as well as checking that the design works first and foremost in monochrome.

Once a first 'dry' (=Mascot-less) version of the Website was ready, QED's Creative Director asked the cartoonist to look at it and to come up with instances of the Mascot that could be placed next to or nearby the various Website section titles: Who We Are, People, What We Do, Results/TRL, News, Contacts. At the same time, the advanced and final version of Rough 01 was given to the Website Designers, to study how to integrate the Mascot in the design.

Various ideas were explored for the instances, which resulted in a first sketch:

Figure 7. Preliminary sketches for Website instances of the MINEON Mascot

The instances were evolved from the initial sketch, with input from the Creative Director, Luca Giberti. For instance, the “Contacts” instance was completely overhauled for clarity, whilst the “People” instance was reviewed to feature the same composition of the famous “The Fourth Estate” painting by divisionist painter Giuseppe Pellizza Da Volpedo. All instances underwent fine tuning.

Figure 8. Sketches for the second and third version of the MINEON Mascot instance for the “People” Website section

Figure 9. Sketches for the second and third version of the MINEON Mascot instance for the “Contacts” Website section

The instances were developed in consultation between the Creative Director, the Cartoonist, and the Website Designers. Feedback from the Website Designers resulted in the request for an extra instance for the top of the main page. As it is customary at QED, the work evolved by selection, but also through a form of 'horizontal gene transfer', i.e. by sometimes grafting features from one design to another: for example, the final design for the additional instance resulted from the Website Designers deciding to use one of the first pictures in the advanced version of Rough 01, but turning it upside-down.

Figure 10. Sketches for two versions of the additional MINEON Mascot instance for the top section of the Website main page

The final versions were completed with the shadows and the yellow colour scheme, for harmonisation with the Website graphics:

Figure 11. Final versions of the MINEON Mascot instances for the top and “Who We Are” Website sections

Figure 12. Final versions of the MINEON Mascot instances for the “People” and “What We Do” Website sections

Figure 13. Final versions of the MINEON Mascot instances for the “Results/TRL” and “News” Website sections

Figure 14. Final version of the MINEON Mascot instance for the “Contacts” Website section

The instances of the Mascot were also used to produce custom MINEON stickers for Whatsapp, which were well-received by project staff and immediately put to use:

Figure 15. The MINEON stickers for Whatsapp

1.3 THE MINEON LOGO AND FAVICON

A cartoon-based Logo offers many advantages:

- in the crowded panorama of corporate and institutional communication, it is highly distinctive and personal;
- its reproduction on screens and in video usually poses no problem of aliasing, due to the finite thickness of the cartoonist's trait;
- its reproduction in offset print is straightforward and free of artifacts, provided one chooses colours wisely from the available CMYK gamut;
- its reduction or adaptation to thumbnail/favicon for social media and browsers poses no problems of aliasing of fine details.

Once the final version of the Mascot was approved, we sought the right instance to be used for the Logo. The Creative Director in the end chose to use one of the very first studies for the character:

Figure 16. Advanced study of the MINEON Mascot in its instance for the Logo

The final instance for the Logo was completed by adding shadows and the yellow colour scheme, then matching it to the fully-capitalised project title. The final result was framed, also for ease of use when lining the logo up in printed documents:

Figure 17. The MINEON Logo

After the Logo, we proceeded to design other essential MINEON graphics, i.e.:

- the Home screen/Springboard shortcut icon for mobile
- the profile picture for possible use in social media
- the favicon for browser tabs
- the Whatsapp Group icon.

Initially, for recognisability, we sought to use one graphic element for the three types of assets.

The first option for the shortcut icon was a rework of the Mascot's head to fit well into a square::

Figure 18. Study of the MINEON Mascot in its Home screen/Springboard shortcut icon version

However, the Creative Director thought that for reasons of brand recognisability it would have been better to feature a portion of the Logo, using the exact same facial expression for the Mascot. Two versions of the disembodied head, inscribed in a square, were prepared, with and without neck. In the end the choice fell on the neck-less version.

Figure 19. second version of the MINEON Mascot in its Home screen/Springboard shortcut icon version

Figure 20. The MINEON Mascot in its final Home screen/Springboard shortcut icon version. The same image can be used as the profile picture for social media

Figure 21. Mock-up of the MINEON Springboard icon in use

Soon in the study of the icon for mobile it became clear that, however, it wouldn't be possible to use the same design for the browser favicons and the Whatsapp groups, since it contained too much detail, which would be lost with the rasterisation. It was decided that the distinctive spiral monocle of the Mascot would work better when rasterised to low resolution.

Figure 22. The MINEON browser favicon and Whatsapp Group icon

2 THE MINEON WEBSITE

The following domain has been registered for the project website:

<http://www.mineon.eu/>

The Website is the reference point of the project's communication and dissemination strategy, as well as a tool for work for the partners.

2.1 FUNCTIONS OF THE PROJECT WEBSITE

The MINEON website is the first port of call for anyone wanting to know more about the project. At the same time, it is also MINEON's own visiting card, so to speak.

Other important features of the website are:

- its usefulness for journalists and media people, who can download press kits and photos;
- further to this, its operational function as an online point-of-access to all of the project's Open Access output: research papers, documents, open data;
- its news feature, which acts as the very first publishing outlet for news about MINEON, which will then be re-posted to social media.

Due to this multitude of needs, the website was conceived and designed based on criteria of clarity, functionality, simplicity, and beauty. Everything is intended to drive the user's attention towards the main function of the website: to provide information about the MINEON project, its activities, progress, and achievements.

Since the Internet has become a mostly mobile medium, the website was conceived from the outset to be smartphone- and tablet-compatible. That is why we adopted a responsive web design solution, i.e. *"...a Web design approach aimed at crafting sites to provide an optimal viewing experience – easy reading and navigation with a minimum of resizing, panning, and scrolling - across a wide range of devices (from desktop computer monitors to mobile phones)"* (Wikipedia). Having said so, given its intended target audiences (which comprise other fellow scientists, journalists, investors, and science buffs - see next chapter), the main scenario of use of MINEON's website is via desktop browser.

The MINEON website is W3C compliant.

Figure 23. The MINEON Website is conceived for both desktop and mobile use

2.2 STRUCTURE AND LAYOUT BASED ON TARGET USERS

The website structure and the design of its graphical user interface were conceived bearing in mind the main scenarios of use and the resulting 'user trajectories' from the moment users land on the home page until they reach the information they seek. Model readers thus considered include the following three macro categories: users interested in knowing more about the project (including investors and schools), scientists managers and admins working in scientific research, journalists.

The logical layout of the main navigation bar (see below) results in the fastest possible path from landing on the home page to retrieving the desired information.

On the other hand, users who are just generally curious are invited to dwell on the rich, high-resolution scientific imagery on which the design is based. Striking visuals are one of the key features of the MINEON website and of the MINEON communication strategy in general. They are the easiest way to begin communicating and generating interest in complex information, not only amongst professionals but also, crucially, within the general public. Besides this, all modern media channels -including social media such as Instagram, Facebook, but also messaging platforms such as Whatsapp, Signal, Snapchat- are mostly or even exclusively image-centric.

A limited colour palette of black, white, gray, and yellow was employed throughout. This is due to several reasons: primarily, to make the website stand out in the hyper-crowded and multicoloured landscape of the Web; but also, in order to make the few colour elements within it stand out, which is especially useful for highlighting items of great importance - such as the EU flag.

As a deliberate choice, the website eschews animations in favour of moveable slides and pictures revealing the Mascot instances and significant images taken from the research papers leading to MINEON.

The website structure and content will evolve in time according to the needs of the project and of its partners.

2.2.1 Home page

The landing (home) page of the website is a clean-looking and intuitive access point from which all further navigation ensues.

It features large backgrounds derived from papers that laid the foundations of MINEON's work. In the upper portion of the landing page is the main navigation bar. The rest of the page, divided into 6 sections, provides all the essential information about the project. At the bottom of the page the user will find the EU flag and the "This project is funded by the EU" caption.

The main navigation bar

The horizontal navigation bar features the following links to the various page sections (NB: the texts for each of the sections are given in Annex 1).

Who We Are

A brief description of the MINEON Partners, with links to their respective websites.

Figure 24. MINEON Website “Who We Are” section

People

The People section was set up in order to offer details of the project staff (bios, recently-completed projects, etc.). It features the Principal Investigators' bios.

Figure 25. MINEON Website “People” section

What We Do

A brief description of the project objectives, featuring a summary of its overall mission and activities.

Figure 26. MINEON Website “What We Do” section

Results/TRL

An overview of MINEON's expected results.

Figure 27. MINEON Website “Results/TRL” section

News

The News section provides a choice of items, each of which can be clicked for further information. This section will be further enriched in the future.

Figure 28. MINEON Website “News” section

It provides news about the project in a standard, easy-to-read format. It is strongly connected with the social networking environment (Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter, Instagram), i.e. News items are also posted on Q-SORT's social media channels, and, conversely, links to follow Q-SORT's social media profiles are provided. This is a critical step towards successful dissemination and community engagement in this technological age. As far as possible, images will be employed to communicate each entry.

This section will feature news and events that are relevant for the MINEON community, including diary-like updates about MINEON progress, of projects that have invited MINEON partners to promote the its activities, and of other events of interest for the MINEON community and target users.

Contacts

An easy-to-read access point for communicating with the MINEON team.

Figure 29. MINEON Website “Contacts” section

EU Funded

A brief introduction to the EC and EC projects, with special emphasis on EIC.

Figure 30. MINEON Website “EU Funded” section

[MINEON logo button]

A button for getting back to the top of the home page, featuring a miniature version of the Mascot instance for the top of the page.

3 TECHNICAL INFRASTRUCTURE

The Content Management System that has been selected as the base technology for the MINEON website is WordPress¹ - a free, open-source blog tool and publishing platform licensed under the GNU General Public License (GPL). WordPress is powered by PHP and MySQL and can easily be customised into a Content Management System (CMS). It has been selected as the base technology for the implementation of the MINEON website because of its flexibility, its user-friendly setup and usage, and its provision of a high level of personalisation. Moreover, its widespread availability has spawned a rich ecosystem of plug-ins, which allow users and developers to extend its functionality beyond the features that come with the base installation. This ensemble of qualities makes WordPress the ideal facilitator of a versatile CMS. Moreover, since it is available for free, it represents maximum value for money.

WordPress has a web template system that uses a template processor. The processor makes it easy to re-arrange widgets and install and switch between themes. The PHP and HTML code used by the themes can also be edited for more advanced customisations.

WordPress has a number of useful features, which include integrated link management, a search-engine-friendly, clean permalink structure; the ability to assign nested, multiple categories for articles; support for tagging of posts and articles. Automatic filters are also included, providing standardised formatting and styling of text within articles.

Multimedia files such as images, videos, flash movies, image galleries, slideshows, etc. can be uploaded and linked to (or displayed in) pages and articles, or embedded directly from other places (e.g. YouTube).

WordPress provides several ready-to-use options for the display of website archives. They can be arranged according to year, month, week, day, category, or author. New archives can be created and easily linked. Since WordPress generates pages dynamically, all these archive pages come at no additional space-cost to the server.

WordPress' built-in search functionality allows visitors to the website to search for terms they are interested in; the search terms are highlighted, making it even easier for them to find what they were looking for.

WordPress supports the Trackback² and Pingback³ standards for displaying links to other sites that have themselves been linked to a post or article.

Hosting was arranged externally, using value-for-money criteria and a tried-and-trusted provider.

4 SERVICES AND OTHER WEBPAGES

4.1 SOCIAL NETWORK INTEGRATION

The MINEON website allows for easy, one-click sharing, bookmarking, and emailing of articles and pages through the provision of a large variety of services.

In particular, AddThis is the add-on tool intended to make sharing and bookmarking simple, and to place at the immediate disposition of users all of the leading web 2.0 social networking, bookmarking, blogging, and email services⁴. Once added, visitors to the website can bookmark an item using through services such as Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, and many more. MINEON Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, and Instagram pages will be created in order to engage a wider public made up of both professionals and nonprofessionals.

The updating of the Facebook page is done either automatically or manually by the authorised managers; automatic updating is based on feeds taken from the MINEON website and the posting of news and select

¹ www.wordpress.org

² www.sixapart.com/pronet/docs/trackback_spec

³ www.hixie.ch/specs/pingback/pingback

⁴ The code is available at www.addthis.com/

memes of interest to the MINEON target audience. Authorised managers can manually post information about events or other relevant information related to the project or partners, as well as select content proposed by the partners. QED is responsible for managing the social network pages.

4.2 WEBSITE STATISTICS

Website usage is monitored through Google Analytics, a very popular Web analytics solution that provides many insights into one's website traffic and marketing effectiveness. It allows for Advanced Segmentation, Custom Reports, Advanced Analysis Tools, Analytics Intelligence, Custom Variables, and Data exports⁵.

Google Analytics can track visitors from all referrers, including search engines, display advertising, pay-per-click networks, email marketing, and digital 'collateral' such as links within PDF documents.

The service offers the following specific statistical insights:

- number of visits and number of unique visitors
- visit duration and last visits
- domains/countries of visitors
- host list, last visits and unresolved IP addresses list, most viewed, entry and exit pages
- browsers used
- robot visits
- search engines, keyphrases and keywords used to arrive at site

Statistics are managed by the webmaster; they are analysed on a tri-monthly basis in order to verify trends and variations.

4.3 FURTHER WORK ON DATA GATHERING AFTER FIRST WEBSITE RELEASE

In order to gain more insights into user behaviour, two scripts will be considered for addition to the MINEON website code:

1. Facebook Pixel in order to provide more insight on user behaviour besides Google Analytics, and better integration with Facebook. This is especially advantageous given the usefulness of Facebook as a tool for outreach.
2. The free version of Hotjar will also be installed (www.hotjar.com) in order to better characterise the effectiveness of the graphical user interface (GUI) of the Website.

Insights provided by these two tools will be discussed in the future, so as to allow for sufficiently meaningful amounts of data to accumulate.

5 THE CONTENT

5.1 EDITORIAL TEAM

The **Editorial Team** is comprised of the following members:

- the Communication and Dissemination Manager (Dr. Luca Marco Carlo Giberti, QED) and the Project Coordinator (Dr. Vincenzo Grillo, CNR) are in charge of deciding overall strategy and monitoring the activities;
- the Communication and Dissemination Executive (Dr. Raffaella Santucci, QED) is in charge of producing, proofreading, checking, and validating the content and publishing the content on the website.

⁵ For individual features, see <https://marketingplatform.google.com/about/>

The content to be published on the website is provided by all partners; contributions can be sent to the editorial team.

An **Editorial Board** for the website will be established for quality control of the texts of the website through an internal call for participation. Editors in Chief of the Board are Vincenzo Grillo and Luca Marco Carlo Giberti. The texts to be published on the website will be first shared and agreed upon between the members of the Board. In the event of dispute, a simple one-vote-per-partner, with majority voting, can be used for decision making. In a tied situation, the Editors in Chief have the casting vote.

Other content posted only on social media, such as individual images or shared links to other online resources, will be emailed *ex post* to the members of the Editorial Board.

5.2 INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS

The MINEON Project is the sole responsible party for content published on the website; it does not represent the opinion of the European Commission.

The text of the MINEON web pages is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 (by) license⁶. This means that users are free to share (copy, distribute, and transmit), remix (adapt), and make commercial use of the website's editorial content under the following conditions:

- **Attribution** — Work must be attributed in the manner specified by the author or licensor (but not in any way that suggests that they endorse you or your use of the work)

It must be noted, however, that the rights to images and videos published on the website are dependent upon the respective attributions of each content provider and may not fall under the above CC licence. Each image has a specific caption with all relevant information.

All other specific contents may be licensed differently according to agreements with single authors.

⁶ <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/>

6 CONCLUSION

This deliverable describes the work carried out to define the Project's Logo, including the Mascot, and to implement the Project's Website.

It has to be noted that the current release of this deliverable presents the first stage in the development of the Website. The website will be continuously and timely updated along the Project's lifetime, and its structure may change to take into account new requirements.

For the duration of the Project's life, the editorial team will continue to:

- constantly update the content of the website
- publish news and events in a timely fashion
- make project deliverables and other documentation available in a timely fashion.

ANNEX 1: LIST OF THE PAGES IN THE FIRST RELEASE OF THE MINEON WEBSITE

MINEON [=landing page]

Who we are
People
What we do
Results/TRL
News
Contacts
EU Funded

WHO WE ARE

The Consortium has been tailor-made in order to reach project goals as quickly and effectively as possible, but also to attain maximum impact in the scientific world and in society at large. The wide cross-section of skills and geographical spread in the Consortium, as well as its adopted policies, ensure that all requirements of responsiveness and adaptive change, diversity and inclusion, openness and transparency are satisfied. Members of the Consortium complement each other thus: CNR and Forschungszentrum Jülich are world leaders in electron-beam shaping; Thermo Fisher (formerly FEI) is a major world-wide developer and manufacturer of microscopes; QED is a young SME from the creative industry led by an award-winning producer-director.

[CNR-NANO \(Project Coordinator\) — Italy](#)

[QED Film & Stage Productions Ltd. — United Kingdom](#)

[FEI \(Thermo Fisher Scientific\) — The Netherlands](#)

[Forschungszentrum Jülich — Germany](#)

PEOPLE

Vincenzo Grillo is the Scientific Coordinator and Principal Investigator of the Q-SORT Project. He graduated in physics from the University of Genova (110/110 cum laude).

He received his PhD in electron microscopy at the University of Parma, while performing collaborative work with Erlangen university (Germany). In 2001 he was a visiting scientist at the Tokyo Institute of Technology working on cathodoluminescence in TEM. Since 2003 he has been working in the INFN (now absorbed by CNR) as a Senior Fellow researcher in electron microscopy. He has developed innovative TEM-STEM methodology and published the first quantitative use of STEM with HAADF detector for chemical analyses. He is now working on Vortex beams and holographic beam generation. He and his group are now among the world's leading groups in this sector for their work on phase holograms, large vortex beams and the theory of spin-orbit coupling with vortex. In 2015 he was a visiting researcher at the University of Oregon. In 2016 he received the Humboldt Foundation's BESSEL research award for his work on Beam shaping. Dr. Grillo is co-author of at least 100 articles and 5 book chapters. The H-factor of his publications is 31.

Enzo Rotunno graduated magna cum laude in Material Science at the University of Parma in 2010 and obtained his PhD degree in material science from the same institution in 2014. Since 2014 he has had a research fellow position at the Italian National Research Council. During his career he achieved high competence in the field of Transmission Electron Microscopy mastering the main electron imaging, diffraction and spectroscopic techniques, with his main research interest being the study of materials through STEM with HAADF detector and the developed of numerical algorithms for the simulation of the electron-matter

interaction. He currently works in CNR-NANO Quantum e-optics group among the world's leading groups in the field of electron vortex beams, and the theory of spin-orbit coupling with vortex. Recently he has started a theoretical activity related to the development of deep learning techniques for microscopy. Dr. Rotunno is co-author of more than 40 research papers. The H-index of his publications is 13.

[Gian Carlo Gazzadi](#)

[Alberto Roncaglia](#)

[Rafal Dunin-Borkowski](#)

[Amir Hossein Tavabi](#)

[Frank de Jong](#)

[Peter Tiemeijer](#)

[Bert Freitag](#)

[Luca Giberti](#)

[Raffaella Santucci](#)

WHAT WE DO

Electron microscopy allows scientists to measure and image material properties down to the very atomic scale, bringing to fruition Feynman's visionary idea that saw in the electron microscope the main instrument for nanoscience. However, its development has been restricted for many years to improving spatial and energetic resolution, through the adoption of bulky sets of magnetic lenses and multipoles. This approach has begun to feel limiting – since cross-fertilisation with light optics has shown the many possibilities hidden in the newly-acquired capacity to perform electron beam shaping.

In the course of the [Q-SORT FET project](#), we devised and perfected various different techniques to shape electron beams. In particular, Q-SORT pioneered an innovative approach to electron beam shaping based on MEMS technology and complex analogue control of the device. These exciting developments are driving electron microscopy into a new era, which is notable for the newly-acquired capacity to extract novel quantities of interest from the sample, and to better characterise samples which are often too fragile for present-day techniques.

One of the many results we obtained in Q-SORT is the capability to manufacture and operate a spiral phase plate (SPP) for electrons, based on the so-called “chopsticks” design. This is an extremely useful device of the widest applicability, since it produces contrast enhancement (edge enhancement) in sample images – a potentially game-changing feature for weak-phase samples, such as organic tissues & molecules. SPPs can also be used to produce arbitrary vortex beams and Bessel beams, both of which can be useful as advanced probes – e.g. as a tool for EMCD (electron magnetic circular dichroism) or for all experiments making use of vortex beams. Q-SORT scientists were the first in the world to produce working electron SPPs. Although we could manufacture electron SPPs (eSPPs) as holograms etched in a substrate, the object of MINEON is a spiral phase plate based on electrostatic fields. This as well was built during Q-SORT as a prototype. Compared to the semiconductor version, the eSPP has the advantage of producing no attenuation of the electron beam and of being tuneable. These two characteristics make it the ideal method for generating vortex beams.

RESULTS/TRL

MINEON will strengthen European leadership on several levels.

From a technological and innovation viewpoint, the project will take a scientific result obtained in [Q-SORT](#), perfect the design and validation of the prospective product (the eSPP), possibly up to TRL 7, and assess its economic viability both in terms of cost model and of market size.

From a value creation & scientific excellence viewpoint, advanced prototypes of the eSPP will be lent to two other strong research groups.

This is not only useful for further validation & feedback, but also, crucially, lays the foundation for new world-class research collaborations stemming from [Q-SORT](#).

News

MINEON project held its Kick-off Meeting.

On **8 June 2021** the [CNR-NANO](#) institute in Modena hosted the **MINEON Kick-off Meeting** for the official launch and first-ever public presentation of the MINEON Project. Funded by the European Commission under its highly competitive **Future and Emerging Technologies** Programme (**FET**) - **Innovation Launchpad**, the project will run for 8 months starting on 1 June 2021.

The Kick-off event - which is organised by CNR - NANO and supported by QED - brought together leading institutions in the field of electron microscopy and quantum light optics, i.e. CNR-NANO (Project coordinator), the Forschungszentrum Jülich, Thermo Fisher Scientific.

MINEON, whose full name is *MINiaturised Electron Optics for Nano-controlled beams*, was conceived as a continuation of another successful FET project, called Q-SORT (www.qsort.eu).

During the course of Q-SORT, scientists devised an innovative approach to electron beam shaping based on MEMS technology and complex analogue control of the set-up. MINEON will further validate the design of a MEMS-based spiral phase plate (SPP), based on the above approach.

The spiral phase plate, which MINEON will realise for the first time, is predicted to improve the electron-microscope imaging of a vast class of systems, and in particular of biological samples, which are of crucial importance in the field of medicine. Indeed, the fact that these systems are made of light atoms normally causes them to yield low or non-existent contrast. The SPP addresses this problem.

The project -which includes applications to physics, biology, and biochemistry- is expected to have a wide-ranging impact due to the ubiquitous adoption of transmission electron microscopy across many disciplines. Moreover, the MINEON Consortium includes a world-leading company in the electron microscopy sector, FEI - ThermoFisher.

The scientific coordinator and principal investigator of MINEON is Vincenzo Grillo, a senior research fellow at CNR -the Italian National Research Council-, recipient of the prestigious [Humboldt Foundation's Bessel Research Award](#) for his work on beam shaping and scientific coordinator of the project [Q-SORT](#).

The MINEON consortium comprises the following European institutions:

[CNR-NANO](#) (Coordinator) - (Italy)

[QED Film & Stage Productions Ltd.](#) - (United Kingdom)
[FEI - Thermo Fisher Scientific](#) - (Netherlands)
[Forschungszentrum Jülich](#) - (Germany)

Caption:
One of the earlier MEMS prototypes realised during the Q-SORT project.
This technology allows for a basic control of the boundary conditions of the spiral phase plate.

CONTACTS

Project Coordinator
Vincenzo Grillo
vincenzo.grillo@cnr.it

Communication Manager
Luca Marco Carlo Giberti
lmcg@qedproductions.co.uk

Executive Manager

Raffaella Santucci

raffaella@qedproductions.co.uk

EU FUNDED

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As part of its remit, the EC directly funds trans-national scientific research projects through dedicated calls for entries, such as those of the FET Programme. We would like to thank the European Union for making MINEON possible. We recognise its important function in promoting the advancement of knowledge and in helping to establish fruitful international long-term relationships involving institutions and companies. We believe that these efforts help us all to better understand and appreciate our cultural diversity.

ANNEX 2: ABBREVIATIONS

SHORT NAME OF PARTICIPANTS

Partner	Country	Short Name
1 CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE	ITALY	CNR
2 QED FILM & STAGE PRODUCTIONS LTD	UNITED KINGDOM	QED
3 THERMO FISHER SCIENTIFIC	THE NETHERLANDS	FEI
4 FORSCHUNGSZENTRUM JÜLICH	GERMANY	FZJ

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Consortium Agreement	CA
Description of Action	DoA
Description of Work	DoW
European Commission	EC
Grant Agreement	GA
Kick-off Meeting	KoM
Project Management Board	PMB
Work Package	WP
Work Package Leader	WPL